

DGIP-CEDS

Data Governance and Intellectual Property Governance
in Common European Data Spaces

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1 Introduction: project summary

The development of a data-driven economy that capitalises on the potentials of digital transformation could bring huge benefits across sectors and domains (such as the provision of more personalised healthcare, improved energy efficiency or more efficient transport systems), but it also poses significant risks and challenges (including the necessity to mitigate/eliminate risks and balance often competing rights and interests associated with data usage). To maximise those potentials, in its European Strategy for Data (2020), the Commission set forth to create a single market for data by setting rules on access to, sharing of and reuse of data, supplemented by the development of Common European Data Spaces in a broad range of sectors and domains. In support of those efforts, during the 2019–24 political mandate, the EU adopted several horizontal legislative acts (Data Governance Act, Data Act, AI Act), as well as the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation, the first sectoral legislative framework for a Common European Data Space. However, certain aspects of those legislative acts have been criticised by stakeholders for failing to ensure legal consistency, fair allocation of rights and responsibilities and due mitigation/elimination of data protection and intellectual property (IP)-related risks.

Acknowledging the pressing challenges ahead of its 2024–2029 mandate, the European Commission has pledged to draw on existing data rules to ensure a simplified, clear and coherent legal framework for data sharing at scale under the (forthcoming) European Data Union Strategy. At the same time, as numerous EU-funded data space pilot projects are making strides, discussions on the creation of Common European Data Spaces are expected to enter a more advanced (possibly legislative) stage in further sectors and domains. In anticipation of those developments, the ‘Data Governance and Intellectual Property Governance in Common European Data Spaces’ (DGIP-CEDS) project analyses how existing and future legislative frameworks (and accompanying contractual frameworks) could be fine-tuned or conceptualised to ensure the adoption and implementation of fair data economy principles in Common European Data Spaces. DGIP-CEDS intends to contribute to EU policy developments by identifying cross-sector commonalities and developing, where possible, common or similar data governance and related IP governance solutions, which could be adopted or implemented across different sectors or domains. As Common European Data Spaces are being developed in sectoral or domain-specific silos, DGIP-CEDS seeks to aggregate and transmit knowledge between the development of data spaces to support the adoption of adequate, effective and consistent legal frameworks.

2 Communication and dissemination: general objectives

This Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) outlines the communication and dissemination objectives of the DGIP-CEDS project. The purpose of the CDP is to strategically determine how the project's activities and results will be shared with various audiences to raise awareness about specific issues, promote knowledge transfer in and beyond the relevant professional, academic and research communities, and ensure that the project's outputs are easily findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (in accordance with the FAIR principles).

Specifically, the purpose of the CDP is to:

- define the communication and dissemination activities of the project (including their form, scheduling, location or channel, target audience(s), key performance indicators [KPIs] and facilitating measures) in order to ensure tailored and effective outreach;
- plan, manage and monitor communication and dissemination activities in order to adapt to evolving needs and maximise the potential impact throughout the project lifecycle;
- inform and engage peers, policymakers, other stakeholders, university students and the general public (at European, national and local level) about the project's objectives, progress and outcomes, demonstrating its value and potential applications to citizens and various professional, academic and research communities;
- increase the potential societal, economic and scientific impact and legacy of the project;
- ensure conformity with the applicable provisions of Grant agreement no.: 101210413 — DGIP-CEDS and relevant Horizon Europe guidelines and best practices.

3 Communication and dissemination roadmap

3.1 Deliverables

<i>Type of activity</i>	<i>Timing</i>	<i>Location or channel</i>	<i>Target audience</i>	<i>KPIs and facilitating measures</i>
Typology of data governance and IP governance in Common European Data Spaces (D1.1)	2025, Q4	Open Research Europe	Experts	Promotion of publication on project website and other channels
Impact analysis of data governance and IP governance in the implementation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) (D2.1)	2026, Q2	Open Research Europe	Experts	Promotion of publication on project website and other channels
Legal solutions to support the conceptualisation of data governance and IP governance requirements in Common European Data Spaces (D3.1)	2027, Q1	Open Research Europe	Experts	Promotion of publication on project website and other channels

3.2 Conference presentations and other publications

<i>Type of activity</i>	<i>Timing</i>	<i>Location or channel</i>	<i>Target audience</i>	<i>KPIs and facilitating measures</i>
Scientific paper on fair data economy principles in Common European Data Spaces (D5.2)	2026 (submission)	International conference proceedings or journal on digital policy / EU law / e-government or Open Research Europe	Experts (digital policy / EU law / e-government)	Submission to: a) conference proceedings, if the previous conference had more than 200 participants, b) Q1/Q2 journal (Scopus), or c) Open Research Europe Promotion of publication on project website and other channels
Conference presentation on fair data economy principles in Common European Data Spaces (<i>extra project</i>)	2026	International conference on digital policy / EU law /	Experts (digital policy / EU law /	International conference with more than 200 on-site participants

<i>activity facilitating the dissemination of D5.2)</i>		e-government (TBC)	e-government)	Promotion of presentation on project website and other channels
Conference presentation on data governance and intellectual property (IP) governance issues in the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation (D5.4/I)	2025	International conference: European Policy for Intellectual Property (EPIP) 2025 Conference (confirmed)	Experts (IP law and policy)	International conference with more than 300 on-site participants Promotion of presentation on project website and other channels
Conference presentation on data governance and intellectual property (IP) governance issues in the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation (D5.4/II) (<i>extra project activity supplementing D5.4/I</i>)	2025	International conference: 17th World Conference Bioethics, Medical Ethics and Health Law (confirmed)	Experts (health law and medical ethics)	International conference with more than 500 on-site participants Promotion of presentation on project website and other channels
Scientific paper on data governance and intellectual property (IP) governance issues in the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation (D5.5)	2026 (submission)	International journal on IP law and policy (TBC) or Open Research Europe	Experts (IP law and policy, healthcare)	Submission to: a) Q1/Q2 journal (Scopus), or b) Open Research Europe Promotion of publication on project website and other channels
Conference presentation(s) on conceptualising data governance and IP governance requirements in future Common European Data Spaces (D5.6)	2025 – 2027	International conference(s) on digital law and policy with relevance to data space developments (TBC)	Experts (digital law and policy, data space developers and implementers)	International conference(s) with key stakeholders (from Croatia and the EU) Promotion of presentation(s) on project website and other channels

3.3 Education and transfer of knowledge (within academia)

Type of activity	Timing	Location or channel	Target audience	KPIs and facilitating measures
University workshop on Marie-Skłodowska Curie Actions (MSCA) Postdoctoral Fellowships (D4.2)	2025, Q2	University of Rijeka, Pre-award Research Support Centre	MSCA-PF applicants and mentors	More than 30 doctoral applicants and potential supervisors Promotion of event on university website

University seminar on the European Health Data Space (D4.3)	2025/26 academic year	University of Rijeka (Faculty of Medicine)	Medicine and other interested students	More than 50 participants Arrangement of a cross-faculty open seminar
University seminar on Common European Data Spaces (D4.4)	2026/27 academic year	University of Rijeka (Faculty of Law)	Law and other interested students	More than 50 participants Arrangement of a cross-faculty open seminar

3.4 Organisation of events

<i>Type of activity</i>	<i>Timing</i>	<i>Location or channel</i>	<i>Target audience</i>	<i>KPIs and facilitating measures</i>
Organisation of European Researchers' Night on Common European Data Spaces (D5.3)	2025/26 TBC	University of Rijeka	General public	More than 50 participants Promotion of event on university website and national event website
Organisation of a national multi-stakeholder event on the implementation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation <i>(extra project activity linked to the performance of T2.2)</i>	2026	Rijeka or Zagreb	Experts (national health authorities, public health institutions and healthcare stakeholders)	Engagement of key actors involved or affected by developments in digital health (at national level) Promotion of event on project website and other professional channels
Organisation of European multi-stakeholder event "Conference on the Law of Common European Data Spaces" (D5.7)	2027, Q1	Rijeka, Zagreb or Brussels	Experts (European digital law and data space experts)	Engagement of a variety of leading experts involved in the development or implementation of Common European Data Spaces or other related R&I projects (at national or EU level) Promotion of event on faculty website and other professional channels

3.5 Other communication and dissemination activities

<i>Type of activity</i>	<i>Timing</i>	<i>Location or channel</i>	<i>Target audience</i>	<i>KPIs and facilitating measures</i>
Project website (M5.1)	2025, Q2	Project website: https://pravri.uniri.hr/en/project/dgip-ceds/	Experts and general public	Inclusion of link in all project publications and other dissemination materials
Project brochure (T5.1)	2025, Q2	Downloadable from project website: https://pravri.uniri.hr/en/project/dgip-ceds/	Experts and general public	Additional dissemination by e-mail to new expert connections
Wikipedia: creation of new page on Common European Data Spaces (T5.2)	2026	https://en.wikipedia.org (new sub-section)	General public	More than 500 visits per month by 2027, Q1
National news media: (1) article on project goals (T5.2) (2) article(s) on project results (T5.2)	2025, Q1 2026 – 2027, Q1	Novi List (oldest Croatian daily newspaper, published in Rijeka) (print and online)	General public	20,000 (daily print circulation, source: Eurotopics) 6,500,000 (total monthly online visitors, source: Similarweb)

Note: The abovementioned abbreviations denote the tasks (T), milestones (M) and deliverables (D) of the project work packages, as defined in the Grant Agreement.

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[DGIP-CEDS project website](#)

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